

Optimising Shielded State Synchronization with FMD and TEEs

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Abstract

In this paper, we propose an efficient solution for the *shielded message recovery problem* based on Fuzzy Message Detection, which also employs trusted enclaves for defense-in-depth. We suggest leveraging multiple detection servers. Being in a *threshold* setting let us strike a sweet balance between privacy and efficiency.

Keywords: FMD ; TEE ; shielded state synchronisation ;

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1. Introduction

Modern decentralized systems emphasize exchanging information anonymously. Inspired by Zcash [HBHW], the de facto approach is having senders encrypting their data with a key-private asymmetric encryption scheme [BBDP01] using the public key of the receiver, and widely publishing the ciphertext —the so-called shielded message. This blueprint is present in the multi-asset shielded pool (MASP) of the Namada blockchain to implement *shielded transfers*, and planned in the Anoma protocol for the more general concept of *shielded states* (resources).

The shielded message recovery problem. No information about the recipient identity is leaked from the shielded message. So, how do receivers identify the messages intended for them? A naive solution is to retrieve all the shielded messages and try to decrypt them to see if the content makes sense. This imposes significant communication and computational overheads, perhaps too much if the receiver is resource-limited (e.g., a wallet software running on a phone).

Retrieving shielded messages efficiently is an active area of research. Ad-hoc solutions include Zcash light client [Tan], and in-device smart scanning [Gri]. Fancier cryptographic primitives have also been crafted for this specific problem: Fuzzy Message Detection (FMD) [BLMG21], Oblivious Message Retrieval [LT22], Private Signaling [MSS⁺22], or designs based on trusted enclaves (TEEs) [WMS⁺19, LHA⁺20].

Our contributions. In this paper, we explain how to thresholdize FMD, and show that it can filter messages efficiently without compromising privacy. We also explain how to shorten and randomize the FMD public key, and how servers can rotate detection keys transparently. Concrete constructions based on the FMD2 scheme [BLMG21] are presented. In addition, we discuss a defense-in-depth methodology using TEEs, provide extensive background on state-of-the-art attacks against TEEs, and detail our solution’s threat model, properties, and countermeasures. We believe this will help us make informed decisions during the deployment of the solution.

2. Preliminaries

2.1. Fuzzy Message Detection

Fuzzy message detection (FMD), introduced by Beck et. al. in [BLMG21], is a primitive to outsource detection of messages to an untrusted server. Senders attach messages with ciphertext flags \vec{f} generated with a public key pk , and receivers give the server a detection key dsk (associated with their pk) to test flags. Detection keys identify matching flags with probability 1, and non-matching flags with probability p , where p is a false-positive detection rate p associated with dsk . The so-called *fuzzy* property.

Detection ambiguity. To hide receiver's messages to the untrusted detection server, a false positive must be indistinguishable from a true positive. To be meaningful, indistinguishability should hold against adversaries (servers) that know the detection key, but it is assumed that ciphertext flags and the FMD keypair are generated honestly by the sender and receiver, respectively.

FMD2 construction. Given a set of false-positive rates \mathcal{P} , an FMD scheme is a tuple of algorithms (KeyGen, Extract, Flag, Detect) defined as follows.

- $\text{KeyGen}(pp_{\text{fmd}})$: On input public parameters pp_{fmd} , produces an FMD keypair (sk, pk) .
- $\text{Extract}(sk, p)$: On input a secret key sk and a false-positive rate p outputs a detection key dsk . (Or error if the rate is invalid $p \notin \mathcal{P}$.)
- $\text{Flag}(pk)$: On input a public key pk , outputs a ciphertext flag \vec{f} .
- $\text{Detect}(dsk, \vec{f})$: On input a detection key dsk and a flag ciphertext \vec{f} outputs a decision bit signaling whether \vec{f} was generated using the public key associated to dsk .

We will be concerned solely with the FMD2 scheme from [BLMG21], described in Figure 1 for completeness. It is based on ElGamal encryption. For security parameter λ , the public parameters pp_{fmd} include the description of a group \mathbb{G} of prime order $q(\lambda)$, a fixed basepoint $B \in \mathbb{G}$, and a constant $\gamma \in \mathbb{N}^+$. The secret key are γ scalars $sk = (x_1, \dots, x_\gamma)$. The public key are γ points $pk = (H_1, \dots, H_\gamma)$. We shall call each scalar x_i (point H_i) of the secret key vector (public key vector) a secret (public) subkey. The set of valid rates is $\mathcal{P} = \{2^{-n} \mid n \in [\gamma]\}$.

2.2. Trusted Execution Environment

A trusted execution environment (TEE) is a secure area within a processor that provides confidentiality, integrity, and isolation for code execution and

<p>KeyGen(pp_{ind}):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1: For $i \in [Y]$: 2: $x_i \xleftarrow{\\$} \mathbb{Z}_q, H_i \leftarrow [x_i] \cdot B$ 3: $sk \leftarrow (x_1, \dots, x_Y)$ 4: $pk \leftarrow (H_1, \dots, H_Y)$ 5: Output sk, pk <p>Extract($sk, p = 2^{-n}$):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1: $(x_1, \dots, x_Y) \leftarrow sk$ 2: If $n > Y$: 3: Output \perp 4: Else: 5: $dsk \leftarrow (x_1, \dots, x_n)$ 6: Output dsk 	<p>Flag(pk):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1: $(H_1, \dots, H_Y) \leftarrow pk$ 2: $r, z \xleftarrow{\\$} \mathbb{Z}_q$ 3: $U \leftarrow [r] \cdot B$ 4: $W \leftarrow [z] \cdot B$ 5: For $i \in [Y]$: 6: $k_i \leftarrow H(U, [r] \cdot H_i, W)$ 7: $c_i \leftarrow k_i \oplus 1$ 8: $m \leftarrow G(U, c_1, \dots, c_Y)$ 9: $y \leftarrow (z - m)r^{-1} \pmod q$ 10: $\vec{f} \leftarrow (U, y, c_1, \dots, c_Y)$ 11: Output \vec{f} 	<p>Detect(dsk, \vec{f}):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1: $(x_1, \dots, x_n) \leftarrow dsk$ 2: $(U, y, c_1, \dots, c_Y) \leftarrow \vec{f}$ 3: $m \leftarrow G(U, c_1, \dots, c_Y)$ 4: $W \leftarrow [m] \cdot B + [y] \cdot U$ 5: For $i \in [n]$: 6: $k_i \leftarrow H(U, [x_i] \cdot U, W)$ 7: $b_i \leftarrow k_i \oplus c_i$ 8: If $b_i = 1 \forall i \in [n]$: 9: Output 1 10: Else: 11: Output 0
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Figure 1. The FMD2 scheme from [BLMG21]. H, G are two cryptographic hash functions.

data processing. It ensures that sensitive computations remain protected from unauthorized access, even from higher-privileged entities like the operating system.

There are process-based TEEs ([Inta]) and VM-based TEEs ([Intb], [AMDA], [IBM], [ARM], [SPS+23]). Process-based TEEs provide secure enclaves within a single process, VM-based TEEs isolate the entire VM from the host environment.

Some of the most popular TEE solutions in use include Intel SGX, ARM SEV, and Intel TDX.

Intel SGX. Intel SGX is a trusted execution environment that allows creating application enclaves running verified code protected by Intel hardware and Intel-developed-and-verified software. The developer writes a program, loads it into an SGX enclave, and SGX provides integrity via remote attestation mechanism and confidentiality via memory encryption.

SGX enclaves can produce local and remote attestations. Local attestations are used to prove integrity to another enclave on the same platform, remote attestations are used to prove integrity to a third party.

To produce a local attestation, the attesting enclave generates a report, which includes the enclave's measurement (a hash of its content). The SGX-enabled CPU signs the report with a key associated with the receiver enclave. The receiver enclave uses its key to verify the produced report.

Remote attestation mechanism is based on the local attestation mechanism. The attesting enclave generates a local report signed with the **quoting enclave's** key. A quoting enclave is a special enclave developed by Intel that produces remote attestations. It verifies the local report and transforms it into a remote report (quote). The quote is signed by the attestation key associated with the SGX. The produced quote is then sent to IAS (Intel Attestation Service) to verify the correct binding between the attestation key and the platform and perform some other checks. After IAS verifies the quote, it is sent to the challenger to verify the enclave's measurement.

The challenger can verify the integrity of the running in the enclave code by recomputing the hash of the binary of the program that is supposedly running in the enclave and comparing to the hash included in the quote. This implies that the SGX integrity mechanism relies on reproducible builds - compiling the same program with the same settings produces the same binary - which is often not the case. That means that, in order to support integrity checks, the developer of the SGX program must ensure the challenger can reproduce the binary.

Intel TDX. Intel TDX (Trust Domain Extensions) is a confidential computing architectural feature launched in 2023 with a new generation of Intel Xeon processors. Intel TDX supposedly provides better abstractions compared to Intel SGX and eliminates some bugs and inconveniences introduced by Intel SGX.

Intel TDX enables TEE environments at the virtual machine level as opposed to Intel SGX that operates at the process level. It assumes an untrusted hypervisor and ensures that the virtual machine (called trust domain in TDX parlance) is protected from a malicious hypervisor. Intel TDX main components:

1. Intel-VT is a hardware-assisted virtualisation mechanism. Intel-VT uses a special instruction set (VMX) to enable virtualisation, SEAM (Secure Arbitration Mode) is an extension of VMX that supports TDX.
2. Intel MKTME. TME encrypts memory, MKTME - multi-key TME - supports memory encryption (AES-XTS) for multiple trust domains.
3. Intel SGX is used to produce attestations
4. TDX module. Given that the hypervisor is assumed to be untrusted, TDX Module acts like a trusted hypervisor that ensures that TD is protected from the outside environment.

One major downside of TDX compared to SGX is that it is quite new and there is not enough information about it and supporting tools to work with TDX. While TDX seems to support legacy code deployment, it requires a TDX-compatible guest OS, which already exist [[The](#), [Ubu](#)].

ARM SEV. Similarly to TDX, AMD SEV allows protecting VMs in an untrusted environment and provides confidentiality and integrity.

VM state is encrypted, the keys are managed by AMD Secure Processor. AMD Secure Processor is a separate isolated processor in AMD CPUs and is similar to a TPM (trusted platform module).

AMD SEV supports remote attestations. Versioned Chip Endorsement Key (VCEK) [[AMDb](#)] is a ECDSA (curve P-384) private key unique to each AMD

chip that is used to sign attestations. The associated public key used to verify the attestations and is signed by AMD (RSA 4096) keys. AMD key distribution system (KDS) allows retrieving VCEK certificates, which in principle allows to perform attestation verification without involving the AMD servers once the VCEK certificate is obtained.

3. System Description

3.1. Design Criteria

The design of the solution is driven by two major goals.

Privacy. The false-positive rate known by a detection server is bounded below by a receiver-defined value p_l .

Efficiency. The effective false-positive rate p_f at which the messages are filtered is upper bounded by p_l .

We call p_l the *leaked* rate, and p_f the *filtering* rate. At first sight, privacy and efficiency seem to be in sharp contradiction with each other. If the detection server is handed out a detection key with at most n secret subkeys in it, the leaked rate is $p_l = 2^{-n}$ and the server cannot filter at lower rates. We resolve by moving to a threshold setting, leveraging multiple detection servers. Since only a strict fraction t of the d servers are *assumed* to be malicious, not all the detection keys are leaked. Section 6 elaborates more on the threat model.

The leaked rate p_l can be dynamically adjusted by each receiver, who may select it according to the (current) number of messages. Saying it differently, receivers are given the ability to choose their own anonymity set for the messages relevant to them¹.

3.2. Parties and communication model

We follow a “pull-based” synchronization. Receivers wishing to obtain fresh messages subscribe with the detection servers by registering their detection keys with them, and periodically obtain FMD filtered messages from the servers. See Figure 2 for a visual overview.

- *Senders.* They create pairs of messages/flags (m, f) . The message m is encrypted with an asymmetric key-private encryption scheme using the encryption key of the intended receiver. The flag f is generated using the FMD public key of the receiver. Senders publish (m, f) in the storage pool.

¹As opposed to Penumbra [Pen]. Therein the sender, not the receiver, chooses the false-positive rate.

- *Receivers.* The recipients of the messages. Receivers multi-extract and register their keys with the detection servers, and are periodically updated with fresh batches of filtered messages from them. They locally combine the filtered messages.
- *Storage Pool.* A public bulletin board where data is stored. Stored data consists in ordered batches $B = (\vec{m}, \vec{f})$. Thus, in each batch, the i -th FMD flag $f_i \in \vec{f}$ is for the i -th message $m_i \in \vec{m}$. (There exists a canonical ordering of the data that everyone agrees with.)
- *Detection Servers.* A set of servers responsible for running FMD detection using the detection keys of the registered receivers. The batch (\vec{m}, \vec{f}) is fetched from the storage pool, and if $\vec{f}' \subseteq \vec{f}$ are the positives for the FMD test, the server sends the associated messages $\vec{m}' \subseteq \vec{m}$ to the receiver.

Remark 1. Other topologies that imply detection servers communication servers can be explored in the future, but we go with the simplest approach.

3.3. Core Components

Multi-key extraction. We extract multiple detection keys from a single secret key. One detection key per server, and each key filtering possibly at different false-positive rates.

Syntax and semantics. In addition to the secret key, the inputs of the multi-extract algorithm are the number of detection keys d , the corruption threshold t , and two false-positive rates p_l, p_f – the leaked and filtering rates.

$$\text{MultiExtract}(sk, d, t, p_l, p_f) \rightarrow (dsk_1, \dots, dsk_d).$$

The leaked and filtering rates are taken from some pre-defined set of valid rates $p_l, p_f \in \mathcal{P}(d, t)$; one set of valid rates per choice of d, t .

Note this is a strict generalization of the syntax and semantics of the FMD extraction defined in [BLMG21] in the threshold setting (see Section 2.1). The non-threshold Extract algorithm can be seen as receiving as input $d = t = 1$ (one server, not trusted) and $p_l = p_f = p$ (leak same rate as the ability to filter).

Furthermore, in the threshold setting, we augment the semantics by requiring that to each subset of $\ell \leq d$ detection keys there is an associated false-positive rate $p(dsk_{j_1}, \dots, dsk_{j_\ell})$ lower bounded by $r(\ell)$. Here $r : \mathbb{N}^+ \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ is a monotonically decreasing rate function. The lower bound is hit by some subset(s) of ℓ keys, in particular $p(dsk_1, \dots, dsk_d) = r(d)$. It is required that $p_l \leq r(t)$ and $p_f = r(d)$.

Figure 2. Filtering messages with three detection servers.

Non-leaking extraction. In the threshold setting, we demand the multi-extraction to be *non-leaking* in the following sense: if d detection keys are extracted from a secret key, the knowledge of any subset of $t < d$ detection keys reveals no information about the other $d - t$ keys.

In Section 4.1 we construct a non-leaking multi-extraction algorithm by slightly modifying the extraction of the FMD2 scheme.

Filter combine. Filtering with different detection keys can be combined. Combining ℓ sets of filtered messages, done with detection keys $dsk_{j_1}, \dots, dsk_{j_\ell}$, respectively, yields a subset of messages filtered at rate $p(dsk_{j_1}, \dots, dsk_{j_\ell})$. This means:

- Receivers, combining d filterings (one per detection server), get messages filtered at rate $r(d) = p_f$.
- Any coalition of $t < d$ servers can only filter at rate $r(t) \geq p_l$. This

follows from the non-leaking property of the multi-extraction, which states that t corrupted servers cannot put together more than t detection keys (and hence, cannot combine more than t filterings).

Combining filterings is very efficient and does not require secret information, so anyone can do it. Importantly, it does not require trial-decryption, which is only run on the combined filtered output. See Section 4.2 for details.

Receiver-side key rotation. Forward secrecy in our setting means that if the detection key of a server is compromised at time t_c , the identity of recipients of messages sent at some past time $t < t_c$ is not leaked. We achieve forward secrecy by letting receivers rotate their keys from time to time.

3.4. Augmentations

In addition to the core functionalities, we describe optional features that can be incorporated into the system.

Key expansion. For FMD2 ([BLMG21]), if we fix $\gamma = 10$, and instantiate the scheme over any popular 256-bit elliptic curve, the size of pk is 320 bytes, which may be too large in some scenarios. For example, if pk is to be part of the receiver address. We augment the syntax of an FMD scheme with two key expansion algorithms.

- $\text{ExpandKeyPair}(csk, cpk) \rightarrow (sk, pk)$. Expand a compact keypair into a pair of secret and public keys.
- $\text{ExpandPublicKey}(cpk) \rightarrow pk$. Expand a compact public key into a public key.

It must hold that $\text{size}(pk_c) < \text{size}(pk)$. The key-expansion algorithms must expand into FMD keys. Thus, extract is defined over the expanded secret key, and flagging is done by first expanding the compact key, and then flagging with the expanded key.

For the case of multi-key extraction, key expansion cannot break the non-leaking property of the detection keys. This means that the size of the compact keypair depends on the chosen corruption threshold t .

Key randomization. Being able to randomize FMD public keys is useful because receivers can create Sybil identities all controlled by the same FMD secret key. As a consequence, a single detection key can be used to filter messages sent to any two Sybil identities. This yields better user experience (UX). Randomization is required so that public keys are unlinkable (for greater privacy), and it should hold against computationally bounded adversaries.

The randomized key is the one produced during key generation. Thus, if $(\tilde{sk}, \tilde{pk}) \leftarrow \text{KeyGen}(pp_{\text{fmd}})$, the randomizer has the following signature

$$\text{Randomize}(\tilde{sk}, \tau) \rightarrow \tilde{pk}'$$

where τ is a public tag. Different tags yield different randomized public keys with overwhelming probability (in the security parameter). The randomization happens either for the FMD public key pk , or, if the scheme supports key expansion, for the compact public key pk_c .

Key expansion and key randomization are compatible if FMD secret keys of FMD public keys expanded from randomized compact keys are the same.

FMD public key randomization was introduced in [Pen] under the name *diversification*. However, their technique is not compatible with key expansion. They had to choose between either having compact public keys or being able to randomize them. In Section 4.3 we describe how to expand onto FMD2 keypairs, and yet being able to randomize the input compact public key.

Server-side key rotation. Key rotation is necessary for forward secrecy, but delegating the responsibility to users means that it might not happen frequently enough, or not happen at all. An alternative is to let detection servers handle the key rotation process periodically, i.e. say every m batches of messages, and in the background, i.e. what is rotated is the servers own keys. Refer to Section 4.4 for more details.

3.5. Parameters

Public parameters. Fixed for all parties. For security parameter λ , the public parameters pp_{fmd} include the description of a group \mathbb{G} of prime order $q(\lambda)$, and a fixed basepoint $B \in \mathbb{G}$. Additionally, they also include:

- $d \in \mathbb{N}^+$. A lower bound on the number of detection servers that are always online.
- $t \in [d-1]$. A corruption threshold. The maximum number of detection servers controlled by the adversary.

Jumping ahead, in the instantiations of Section 4, the public parameters also include:

- $\gamma \in \mathbb{N}^+$. Determines the minimum false-positive detection rate $2^{-\gamma}$, the bitsize of the FMD keys ($O(\lambda\gamma)$ bits), and the bitsize of the ciphertext flags ($O(\lambda + \gamma)$ bits).

Receiver parameters. The leaked and filtering rates $(p_l, p_f) \in \mathcal{P}(d, t)$. Jumping ahead, in the instantiations of Section 4:

- $p_l = 2^{-n}$ for some $n \in [\gamma]$, which is the total number of secret subkeys a coalition of $t < d$ servers can put together.
- $p_f = 2^{-\delta}$ for some $\delta \in [n, \gamma]$, which is the total number of secret subkeys shared with the d detection servers.

4. Concrete Instantiation

4.1. Multi-key Extraction

Index-aware extraction and detection. The scheme FMD2 described in [BLMG21] (see Fig. 1) sets the detection key for rate 2^{-n} to the first n secret subkeys of the receiver $dsk = (x_1, \dots, x_n)$. We slightly modify the extract and detect algorithms. Detection keys dsk are now any ordered subset of n secret subkeys along with the position indices they occupy in the secret key vector. Detecting the flag ciphertexts \vec{f} is done according to the indices.

Splitting the secret key. Suppose there are d servers and at most $t < d$ can be malicious. If the receiver wants to set the leaked rate to $p_l = 2^{-n}$, they split their γ secret subkeys into $t - 1$ subsets of $\lfloor n/t \rfloor$ subkeys each, and one subset with the remaining subkeys. More concretely, define

$$\begin{aligned} n_j &= \lfloor n/t \rfloor \text{ for } j = 1, \dots, d - 1 \\ n_d &= n - (t - 1)\lfloor n/t \rfloor \end{aligned}$$

The j -th detection key is

$$dsk_j = (x_{\sum_{i \leq j} n_i + 1}, \dots, x_{\sum_{i \leq j} n_i}).$$

Such splitting of the secret key into multiple detection keys is *disjoint*, and ensures no coalition of t servers can put together more than n secret subkeys.

<p>MultiExtract(sk, d, t, n, δ):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1: Assert: \triangleright Enforce $(2^{-n}, 2^{-\delta}) \in \mathcal{P}(d, t)$ 2: $t \leq d \leq \gamma$ 3: $t \leq n$ 4: $\delta = n + (d - t)\lfloor n/t \rfloor$ 5: $\delta \leq \gamma$ 6: $(x_1 \dots, x_\gamma) \leftarrow sk$ 7: For $j \in [d]$: 8: If $j < d$ then: $n_j \leftarrow \lfloor n/t \rfloor$ 9: Else $n_j \leftarrow n - (t - 1)\lfloor n/t \rfloor$ 10: If $j = 1$, $\text{id}_{x_j} \leftarrow 1$. Else $\text{id}_{x_j} \leftarrow \sum_{i=1}^{j-1} n_i$ 11: $\{\text{id}_{x_j} + 1, \dots, \text{id}_{x_j} + n_j\} \leftarrow \mathbb{I}_j$ 12: $disk_j \leftarrow ((x_i)_{i \in \mathbb{I}_j}, \mathbb{I}_j)$ 13: $\vec{disk} \leftarrow (disk_1, \dots, disk_d)$ 14: Output \vec{disk} 	<p>Detect($disk, \vec{f}$):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1: $((x_1, \dots, x_n), \{i_1, \dots, i_n\}) \leftarrow disk$ 2: $(U, y, c_1, \dots, c_\gamma) \leftarrow \vec{f}$ 3: $m \leftarrow G(U, c_1, \dots, c_\gamma)$ 4: $W \leftarrow [m] \cdot G + [y] \cdot U$ 5: For $j \in [n]$: 6: $k_j \leftarrow H(U, [x_j] \cdot U, W)$ 7: $b_j \leftarrow k_j \oplus c_{i_j}$ 8: If $b_j = 1 \forall j \in [n]$: 9: Output 1 10: Else: 11: Output 0
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Figure 3. The multi-key FMD scheme mFMD2. Flagging and key generation are exactly as in the FMD2 scheme [BLMG21] (cf. Fig. 1). The difference in the detection is just in line 7, wherein the chosen ciphertext bit c_{i_j} now depends on index i_j .

The multi-key extraction algorithm. Putting the above two pieces together we obtain our multi-key extraction algorithm. Namely, split the secret indices, and extract d subkeys with the index-aware extraction. For chosen $t \leq d \leq \gamma$, the set of allowed rates is

$$\mathcal{P}(d, t) = \left\{ p_l = 2^{-n}, p_f = 2^{-\delta} \mid \begin{array}{l} t \leq n, \\ \delta = n + (d - t)\lfloor n/t \rfloor \wedge \delta \leq \gamma \end{array} \right\},$$

where δ is obtained by summing up the number of (different) subkeys across the d detection keys, $\delta = n_1 + \dots + n_d$.

The multi-FMD scheme mFMD2 is presented in Figure 3.

Any subset of ℓ detection keys can filter at false-positive rate $p(dsk_{j_1}, \dots, dsk_{j_\ell}) = 2^{-\sum_{k \leq \ell} n_{j_k}}$. A lower bound is the function

$$r(\ell) = \min_{(j_1, \dots, j_\ell) \subset [d]} \{2^{-\sum_{k \leq \ell} n_{j_k}}\},$$

which is monotonically decreasing. By construction, it holds $p_l \leq r(t)$ and $r(d) = p_f$ for $p_l, p_f \in \mathcal{P}(d, t)$.

Non-leaking. The knowledge of t detection keys does not give out any information about the other $d - t$ detection keys. This is because the secret subkeys x_i are chosen at random and independent of each other, and each detection key contains different subkeys (the key split is disjoint).

Bandwidth. The size of the detection key determines bandwidth server \rightarrow receiver. Concretely, n_j determines roughly the number of filtered messages sent from the j -th detection server.

Example. Three detection servers $d = 3$ corruption threshold $t = 2$, and $n = 3, \delta = 4$, yields $n_1 = n_2 = 1, n_3 = 2$, the leaked rate is $p_l = 1/8$, and the filtering rate is $p_f = 1/16$.

4.2. Filter Combine

For each FMD flag ciphertext \vec{f} , the j -th server now detects a different subset of ciphertext bits $(c_j, \dots, c_{j+n_j-1})$ of \vec{f} using $ds k_j$. Therefore true or false positives of tests done with the combined detection key $ds k_f = (x_1, \dots, x_\delta)$ lie at the intersection of the positives of tests done individually with $ds k_1, \dots, ds k_d$.

For a batch of messages/flags (\vec{m}, \vec{f}) in the storage pool, let $\vec{m}_j \subseteq \vec{m}$ be the filtered messages done with the j -th detection key $ds k_j$. Combine ℓ such filterings as:

$$\text{Combine}(\vec{m}_{j_1}, \dots, \vec{m}_{j_\ell}) = \cap_{k \leq \ell} \vec{m}_{j_k}.$$

Note that combined messages are filtered at rate at least $r(\ell)$, and if $\ell = d$ the lower bound is hit. Namely, d combined messages are filtered at rate exactly $p_f = r(d) = 2^{-\delta}$.

4.3. Key expansion and randomization

Expanding onto FMD2 keypairs. For a given corruption threshold t , the idea is to use a secret polynomial $p(X) = \sum_{k=0}^t c_k X^k \in \mathbb{Z}_q[X]$ of degree t as the compact secret key sk_c . The corresponding compact public key pk_c is the polynomial in “the exponent” using an arbitrary basepoint. sk_c is represented with the $t + 1$ coefficients of $p(X)$, and pk_c with the $t + 1$ encoded coefficients and the chosen basepoint.

An FMD secret key sk expanded from sk_c are evaluations of $p(X)$ at public scalars $e_1, \dots, e_\gamma \in \mathbb{Z}_q$. Likewise, the expanded public key pk are the encoded evaluations in the exponent, and the chosen basepoint B .

$$\begin{aligned} sk &= (x_1, \dots, x_\gamma) \in \mathbb{Z}_q^\gamma \text{ such that } x_i = p(e_i). \\ pk &= (B, H_1, \dots, H_\gamma) \in \mathbb{G}^{\gamma+1} \text{ such that } H_i = [p(e_i)] \cdot B \end{aligned}$$

Expanding publicly. It is done evaluating the *public* scalars in the exponent, using the encoded polynomial $pk_c = (B, C_0, \dots, C_t)$. Namely,

$$\tilde{pk} = (B, \tilde{H}_1, \dots, \tilde{H}_\gamma) \text{ such that } \tilde{H}_i = \sum_{j=0}^t [e_i^j] \cdot C_j.$$

Clearly, it holds $pk = \tilde{pk}$. The size of the compact keys are $t + 2$ points, where t is the corruption threshold. For any $\gamma > t + 2$ compactness is achieved $size(pk_c) < size(pk)$.

Randomizing compact keys. Different basepoints give raise to different encodings of the secret polynomial. For any $B \neq B'$,

$$pk_c = (B, [c_0] \cdot B, \dots, [c_t] \cdot B),$$

$$pk'_c = (B', [c_0] \cdot B', \dots, [c_t] \cdot B'),$$

are two valid encodings of $p(X) = \sum_{k=0}^t c_k X^k$ in \mathbb{G} . To generate a random basepoint bound to a user's public tag τ , we hash τ into the group \mathbb{G} using a cryptographic hash function $H : \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{G}_q$. Hashed basepoints allows a *compressed* representation of compact keys: $t + 1$ points (instead of $t + 2$ points), and the tag τ . It is compressed because the bitsize of tags can be much smaller than the bitsize of points in \mathbb{G} , and can be set to information already present on the user context.

The compact multi-key FMD scheme. The basepoint B' identifies the FMD public key $pk' = (B', H'_1, \dots, H'_t)$. To avoid leaking information about pk' during detection, each flag operation uses an ephemeral basepoint $B_{ch} = [s] \cdot B'$, with $s \xleftarrow{\$} \mathbb{Z}_q$, for the Chamaleon hash. The ephemeral basepoint is included as part of the FMD flag ciphertexts \vec{f} . The knowledge of s is needed to generate the fake opening y of the equivocation commitment w , which now is set to:

$$y = (z - m)sr^{-1} \pmod{q}.$$

We note that ephemeral basepoints to hide the FMD public keys were first used in the diversification technique from [Pen].

Figure 4 presents all the algorithms of the compact multi-key scheme cmFMD2 discussed so far.

Non-leaking detection keys. With up to t evaluations it is not possible to reconstruct the degree t polynomial $p(X)$. Thus, given any subset of t FMD secret subkeys $p(x_{j_1}), \dots, p(x_{j_t})$, one cannot infer any information about the other FMD secret key scalars $p(x)$, for $x \in \{x_1, \dots, x_y\} \setminus \{x_{j_1}, \dots, x_{j_t}\}$, because $p(X)$ is randomly chosen.

Unlinkable randomized compact public keys. Suppose basepoints B, B' are generated at random, and let us write $B = [r] \cdot G, B' = [r'] \cdot G$, in some fixed and known base $G \in \mathbb{G}$. By the DDH assumption over the prime order group \mathbb{G} , for each coefficient $c_k \xleftarrow{\$} \mathbb{Z}_q$ it holds

$$\begin{aligned} (G, B, B', C_k, C'_k) &= (G, [r] \cdot G, [r'] \cdot G, [rc_k] \cdot G, [r'c_k] \cdot G) \\ &\approx_c (G, [r] \cdot G, [r'] \cdot G, R_k, R'_k) \\ &= (G, B, B', R_k, R'_k), \end{aligned}$$

for randomly chosen points R_k, R'_k . This says that the joint distribution of any two encoded polynomials is computationally close to the uniform distribution in \mathbb{G}^{2t+4} . In other words, any two compact public keys pk_c, pk'_c cannot be linked to each other. Since the basepoints are obtained by hashing into \mathbb{G} , the analysis holds in the random oracle model.

<p>KeyGen(pp_{fmd}):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1: $B \xleftarrow{\\$} \mathbb{G}_q$ 2: For $i \in [t]$: 3: $c_i \xleftarrow{\\$} \mathbb{Z}_q, C_i \leftarrow [c_i] \cdot B$ 4: $sk_c \leftarrow (c_0, \dots, c_t) \in \mathbb{Z}_q^t$ 5: $pk_c \leftarrow (B, C_0, \dots, C_t) \in \mathbb{G}_q^{t+1}$ 6: Output sk_c, pk_c <p>Randomize(sk_c, τ):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1: $(c_0, \dots, c_t) \leftarrow sk_c$ 2: $B' \leftarrow \text{Hash}(\tau)$ 3: For $i \in [t]$: 4: $C'_i \leftarrow [c_i] \cdot B'$ 5: $pk'_c \leftarrow (C'_0, \dots, C'_t) \in \mathbb{G}_q^{t+1}$ 6: Output pk'_c 	<p>ExpandKeypair(sk_c, pk'_c):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1: $(c_0, \dots, c_t) \leftarrow sk_c$ 2: $(B', C'_0, \dots, C'_t) \leftarrow pk'_c$ 3: $(e_1, \dots, e_\gamma) \leftarrow e_{\text{eval}}$ 4: For $i \in [\gamma]$: 5: $x_i \leftarrow \sum_{j=0}^t c_j e_i^j$ 6: $H'_i \leftarrow [x_i] \cdot B'$ 7: $sk \leftarrow (x_1, \dots, x_\gamma) \in \mathbb{Z}_q^\gamma$ 8: $pk' \leftarrow (B', H'_1, \dots, H'_\gamma) \in \mathbb{G}^{\gamma+1}$ 9: Output sk, pk' 	<p>ExpandPublicKey(pk'_c):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1: $(B', C'_0, \dots, C'_t) \leftarrow pk'_c$ 2: $(e_1, \dots, e_\gamma) \leftarrow e_{\text{eval}}$ 3: For $i \in [\gamma]$: 4: $H'_i \leftarrow \sum_{j=0}^t [e_i^j] \cdot C'_j$ 5: $pk' \leftarrow (B', H'_1, \dots, H'_\gamma) \in \mathbb{G}^{\gamma+1}$ 6: Output pk'
<p>Flag(pk'):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1: $(B', H'_1, \dots, H'_\gamma) \leftarrow pk'$ 2: $r, s, z \xleftarrow{\\$} \mathbb{Z}_q$ 3: $U \leftarrow [r] \cdot B'$ 4: $B_{\text{ch}} \leftarrow [s] \cdot B'$ 5: $W \leftarrow [z] \cdot B_{\text{ch}}$ 6: For $i \in [\gamma]$: 7: $k_i \leftarrow \text{H}(U, [r] \cdot H_i, W)$ 8: $c_i \leftarrow k_i \oplus 1$ 9: $m \leftarrow \text{G}(U, c_1, \dots, c_\gamma)$ 10: $y \leftarrow (z - m)sr^{-1} \bmod q$ 11: $\vec{f} \leftarrow (B_{\text{ch}}, U, y, c_1, \dots, c_\gamma)$ 12: Output \vec{f} 	<p>Detect(dsk, \vec{f}):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1: $((x_1, \dots, x_n), \{i_1, \dots, i_n\}) \leftarrow dsk$ // As in mFMD2. See Fig. 3. 2: $(B_{\text{ch}}, U, y, c_1, \dots, c_\gamma) \leftarrow \vec{f}$ 3: $m \leftarrow \text{G}(U, c_1, \dots, c_\gamma)$ 4: $W \leftarrow [m] \cdot B_{\text{ch}} + [y] \cdot U$ 5: For $j \in [n]$: 6: $k_j \leftarrow \text{H}(U, [x_j] \cdot U, W)$ 7: $b_j \leftarrow k_j \oplus c_{i_j}$ 8: If $b_j = 1 \forall j \in [n]$: 9: Output 1 10: Else: 11: Output 0 	<p>MultiExtract(sk, d, t, n, δ):</p>

Figure 4. The compact multi-key FMD scheme cmFMD2. The corruption threshold $t < \gamma$ is part of the public parameter pp_{fmd} . **top:** Key generation, randomization and expansion. **bottom:** Flagging, detection, and multi-key extraction. Flagging is run on the expanded public key pk' .

4.4. Server-side Key Rotation

To implement key rotation on the detection servers, FMD flag ciphertexts $\vec{f} = (u, y, c_1, \dots, c_\gamma)$ are generated using an extra FMD public key $pk_S = (H_{S,1}, \dots, H_{S,\gamma})$ owned by the detection server S . Thus, the detection server knows the private key $sk_S = (x_{S,1}, \dots, x_{S,\gamma})$ such that $pk_{S,i} = [x_{S,i}] \cdot B$. To generate each ciphertext bit c_i , an extra DDH mask $pk_{S,i}^s$ is also hashed, where s is fresh randomness.

Rotating keys. To rotate the keys, the servers engage in a commit-and-reveal protocol. Each server S_j samples and broadcasts a random FMD keypair (sk_j, pk_j) . All keypairs are aggregated to form the joint server keypair. To ensure individual keypairs are independent of each other, they are committed in a first round. This prevents a malicious server control the aggregated keypair, and for example, reuse old keypairs in an attempt to break forward secrecy.

Detection-ambiguity. The modified scheme retains detection-ambiguity. Although the same server FMD key is used for all receivers, FMD flags for different receivers still use different FMD (user) keys.

Liveness. The server FMD keypair does not need to be associated with a particular server identity. If there are multiple servers, they will use the same FMD keypair (sk_S, pk_S) . If one server goes offline, it is still possible to do FMD detection.

Server-side communication. Communication between the servers is necessary at two moments:

- When a new detection server joins the system. The new joiner contacts an existing server to receive the current FMD keypair.
- When the FMD keypair is rotated. This may happen every b batches of messages, where b would be a system parameter.

5. FMD in TEE

5.1. Running the FMD detection protocol in a TEE

The multi-key FMD scheme described in Section 3 can be used to accelerate the detection rate on its own, but it comes at a cost. The detection servers must be trusted not to take advantage of the received information, not collude (above a certain threshold), and to implement sufficient protection measures to keep the user's information safe. Running the FMD protocol in TEEs is one way to tackle these problems and increase the costs of possible attacks. Later in Section 6.2 we discuss two possible ways of doing this.

We assume users communicating directly with TEEs. Remote attestation (see Section 2.2) against the full FMD protocol can help to verify the integrity of the code and make sure that it is indeed executed from inside the TEE.

The user establishes a secure channel with the TEE, sharing a detection key, and receives the filtered messages. The servers are independent of each other and communicate directly with the user, so there is not TEE-to-TEE communication. Refer to Section 3.2 for more details on the communication model.

5.2. Challenges in Developing Applications with TEEs

- **Availability:** The context of the FMD protocol implies that it is to run on multiple nodes that are not assumed to be associated with the protocol developers. The development of the TEE solution requires having access to TEEs, and this is not too easy to arrange. There is a limited amount of cloud providers that provide access to a TEE. They can also strip the functionality in a way that is not enough to test the protocol properly or ensure the required security measures. Owning a server solves these problems, but doesn't allow testing the application against multiple TEEs easily. Some of these concerns are also relevant for the parties running the FMD protocol.

- **Tooling:** Newer TEEs like Intel TDX do not have mature enough tooling to make the development process easier. Some TEEs require building a custom set of supporting tools to enable running the application in that TEE.
- **Reproducible builds:** In plain terms, an integrity attestation is a signature over the state of the enclave/VM running the application executable. To verify that the expected application code is running in the TEE, the code must first be compiled, and then the produced binary is used to verify the signature. This process is based on the assumption that the compilation process is deterministic. Ensuring that the produced executable is the same regardless of what machine it is compiled on and at what time is not trivial. In order to support the integrity feature, the developer must ensure that their application binary is reproducible.
- **Reduced practical integrity benefits:** Due to limited memory access, a poor developer experience, and difficulties in communicating with the external environment that TEEs introduce, the general sentiment is to put as little code as possible in a TEE. Practically speaking, this cancels out some potential integrity properties of the protocol.

6. Security analysis

6.1. Threat Model

The threat model is stated in terms of what the adversary can and cannot do. Firstly, the adversary is computationally bounded, so that the properties of the FMD scheme hold. In addition to this:

- The adversary can perform active and dynamic corruptions.
- The adversary can corrupt up to a strict fraction t of the current online detection servers.
- Honest detection servers can erase part of their internal state. Erased data is not accessible by the adversary if the server is corrupted later on.
- The adversary can observe all network traffic.
- The adversary cannot corrupt senders or receivers.
- The adversary cannot corrupt the storage pool. In particular, it cannot force inserts or deletes of messages, modify content, or alter the existing ordering.

Active corruptions mean that malicious servers may attempt to deviate from the prescribed instructions, or they may leak private receiver information, such as FMD detection keys.

We also assume the existence of confidential and authenticated channels between the honest parties, so the adversary cannot modify nor inspect plaintext data flowing between them.

6.2. Defense in Depth

We adopt a defense in depth approach and use TEEs to limit leakage in case some fraction t of the detection servers are compromised. TEEs can be used in two ways, listed in increased complexity.

Only FMD detection runs in TEEs The adversary will be able to reduce the anonymity set size (to a publicly acceptable degree given by the receivers' leaked rate p_l), but will not be able to learn what exact messages are addressed to a specific receiver, nor decrypt the messages. TEEs deployed in this mode justifies *lower corruption thresholds* t , which in turns yields better efficiency of the solution.

Entire server runs in TEEs Confidentiality and integrity is harder to break. Extracting the communicated data and changing the flow of the application requires the effort of breaking the TEE now, which might simply be not the wisest allocation of resources on the adversary's side. Besides allowing lower thresholds as above, this mode also guarantees a more *robust* system.

Attack Vectors Against TEEs. TEEs are infamous for the amount of attacks that can be hard to mitigate since they often require firmware updates.

Due to their nature, TEE attacks can be divided into two classes based on the mitigation means: attacks that require firmware updates and attacks that do not require firmware updates (can be fully prevented by using application development practices).

Since the developer has little control over defense against the first kind of attacks, the vulnerabilities of that kind define the environment.

To better understand the risks involved, we examine the existing attacks of the first type and adjust our design and threat model to get the best out of TEEs.

Intel SGX seems to be the most studied TEE solution in terms of existing attacks. According to [vSSY⁺22], two thirds of the existing SGX attacks can be mitigated by the developer (half of which is done by employing constant-time code). Most of the attacks that require microcode updates work by leaking enclave information from shared memory: L1 cache [VBMW⁺18], controllers

[BKS⁺22, Dev], via hyper-threading [vSMK⁺21, vSKGY20], etc. At the same time, most of them require root privileges to perform the attack.

Similar is true for attacks on VM-based TEEs: for AMD SEV, among the attacks that require microcode updates to be mitigated, most require root privileges to be executed [SSK⁺24, SSBS24, ZGW⁺24, MPR⁺21].

Intel TDX is relatively new (2023) at the time of writing of this paper (2025) and not a lot of attacks has been discovered. The discovered ones seem to follow the same pattern.

6.3. Properties and Countermeasures

The solution described in Section 3 enjoys a number of properties summarized below.

Properties related to privacy are:

- **The adversary cannot reduce the anonymity size of receivers below a certain bound.** The false-positive rate known by the adversary is higher than the leaked rate p_l chosen by the receiver.
- **Forward secrecy.** If the adversary corrupts a detection server at time t_c , the identity of recipients of messages sent at time $t < t_c$ is not known. Receivers rotate detection keys from time to time, and the honest servers erase rotated keys (the threat model allow erasures.). Updating the detection keys more allows to reduce the amount of the affected flag ciphertexts but require the user to communicate with the detection server more often. With server-side key rotation (cf. Section 4.4), this property is enforced by design.

Robustness is also important because the threat model allows active (byzantine) corruption of the detection servers. Properties related to robustness are:

- **Receivers detect bad filterings.** If the entire server runs in TEEs, deviation from the protocol is noticed. (See section 6.2.)
- **Receivers do not get messages that are not in the storage pool.** Receivers can check themselves against the storage pool. To not break privacy, all messages should be retrieved. This affects communication bandwidth, but *not* computational overhead: trial-decryption is run on the reduced set of messages.

We do not implement any *costly* measures to protect our system against TEE leaks in case the host OS is controlled by the adversary and assume that the host OS is not malicious. But we do implement *simple* measures that allow us to detect unusual behavior and prevent the attacks. These measures are:

- **Verification of the false-positive rates of the detected messages**
The receiver can check that the number of received messages aligns (roughly) with the expected number of detected messages. The latter is inferred from the false-positive rate and the number of messages in the storage pool, both public values.
- **Customizing the amount of time for which the data is stored in a TEE.** Specially sensitive data, like detection keys, could be sent by receivers on each request and erase it immediately after.
- **Relying on most up-to-date TEE platforms.** In case the most up to date servers are not the most popular or bigger ones, in requires the user choosing between better hardware protection vs better reputation and overall protection.

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